

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA FOR Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV} AND Ru^{III} COMPLEXES WITH HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ AND HO-INBTZ

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Molar con- ductance in 10 ⁻³ M DMF Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Ir bands (cm ⁻¹) and tentative assignments*		
				C	S	Cl/N*	Metal/H*	$\nu_{C=N}$ of imine-N	$(\nu_{C=S} + \nu_{C=N} + \gamma_{CN})$	$\nu_{C=S}$
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HS-SABTZ)	Light yellow	137	—	54.81 (54.54)	18.54 (19.39)	17.95* (16.96)*	4.31* (4.21)*	1 650s	1 310s	750vs
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HO-NABTZ)	Buff yellow	127	—	62.26 (62.63)	9.18 (8.79)	15.64* (15.38)*	4.21* (4.39)*	1 635s	1 300s	760vs
C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S (HO-INBTZ)	Yellowish-red	115	—	61.96 (61.53)	9.52 (9.11)	15.27* (15.95)*	4.13* (4.27)*	1 640s	1 395s	755vs
[Pd(-S-SABTZ)Cl]	Orange-red	202	1.43	37.74 (38.30)	14.23 (13.60)	6.32 (7.50)	23.07 (22.63)	1 650s	1 275m	730s
[Pd(-O-NABTZ)Cl]	Dark red	200	5.49	45.78 (45.13)	5.86 (6.33)	6.85 (7.02)	18.90 (18.46)	1 650s	1 275ms	735s
[Pd(-O-INBTZ)Cl]	Dark red	152	0.017	44.32 (43.91)	6.18 (6.50)	6.84 (7.21)	22.25 (21.63)	1 655s	1 270ms	725s
[Pt(S-SABTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	120	171.5	41.27 (42.11)	14.35 (14.84)	7.27 (7.56)	24.12 (23.25)	1 635s	1 270ms	740vs
[Pt(-O-NABTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	86	183.4	48.78 (49.52)	6.63 (6.95)	7.23 (7.05)	22.12 (21.16)	1 635s	1 265ms	725ms
[Pt(-O-INBTZ) ₂ Cl ₂]	Orange	90	175.2	48.53 (48.27)	6.95 (7.15)	7.64 (7.23)	22.16 (21.79)	1 635s	1 270s	720m
[Ru(-S-SABTZ) ₂ Cl]	Greyish yellow	115	94.52	44.78 (45.31)	15.85 (16.11)	4.72 (4.46)	13.05 (12.72)	1 640s	1 370ms	735s
[Ru(-O-NABTZ) ₂ Cl]	Dull grey	98	101.6	53.14 (52.86)	7.75 (7.42)	4.04 (4.11)	12.03 (11.70)	1 645s	1 360ms	730s
[Ru(-O-INBTZ) ₂ Cl]	Dull grey	105	98.7	50.15 (49.51)	7.52 (7.3)	3.84 (4.06)	12.08 (11.77)	1 645s	1 360ms	735s

* vs=very sharp, s=sharp, m=medium, ms=medium sharp.

by using the relation $E^* = (10Dq - 3F_2 - 20F_4)$ assuming $F_2 = 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $F_4 = 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For the Ru^{III} complexes with HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ, the value of μ_{eff} , 10Dq, B and E* are calculated as (0.25, 41 769, 19 and 21 739), (0.19, 43 400, 850 and 23 370) and (0.31 B.M., 46 512 cm^{-1} , 912 cm^{-1} and 16 482 cm^{-1}), respectively, revealing⁷ inner-orbital low-spin distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the ligands around Ru^{III} metal ion.

The sharp absorption bands observed at ~1 300 and ~750 cm^{-1} in the free ligands, assigned⁸ to $(\nu_{C=S} + \nu_{C=N} + \gamma_{CN})$ and $\nu_{C=S}$, respectively, are decreased in frequency (by 20-40 cm^{-1}) as well as weakened in intensity, revealing coordination through thio-keto-sulphur atom. The absence of the band observed in free ligands at 2 320 (HS-SABTZ), 3 300 (HO-NABTZ) and 3 180 cm^{-1} (HO-INBTZ) assigned to ν_{SH} , ν_{OH} and ν_{OH} , respectively, ascertain the participation of the sulphur atom of SH group and oxygen atom of OH group through deprotonation on complexation under study. The sharp absorption bands observed at 1 650, 1 635 and 1 640 cm^{-1} (in the free ligands), attributed to $\nu_{C=N}$ of immine-nitrogen do not exhibit any remarkable red/blue shift in frequency as well as decrease in their intensity, indicating non-involvement of immine-nitrogen in coordination. In all of the present complexes, the medium to weak intensity bands observed in the far-ir, region, viz. 550-500, 450-400 and 350-250 cm^{-1} , tentatively assigned⁸ to $\nu_{M-smido-N}$, ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-Cl} , respectively, also confirm the square-planer and octahedral stereochemistries of

ligands HS-SABTZ, HO-NABTZ and HO-INBTZ around Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV}, and Ru^{III} metal ions, respectively.

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Studies on Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Gallium(III) by Cationic and Anionic Surfactants and by their Mixtures vis-a-vis the Adsorption Characteristics

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A survey of literature reveals that suppression of polarographic maximum of Ca^{III} by surfactants has not been attempted so far. The present paper reports the results of our investigations on

the suppression of polarographic maximum of Ga^{III} by some cationic and anionic surfactants with special reference to the additive and antagonistic effects of their mixtures. The adsorption characteristics of cationic and anionic surfactants separately as well as in their mixtures have also been studied.

Experimental

$\text{Ga}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was a Fluka (A.R.) product. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The depolariser concentration was kept at $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. NaNO_3 (0.05 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal CLO2 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used for measuring the potential and current, respectively. Hydrogen was used for deoxygenation of the solutions. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. Electrocapillary curves were obtained by the drop-time method¹. The dme had the following capillary characteristics (in 0.05 M NaNO_3 , open circuit : $m = 3.317 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.2 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 2.7 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/3}$, $h_{\text{cor}} = 53.2 \text{ cm}$).

Results and Discussion

Representative Figs. 1a-c depict the morphology of C-V curves of Ga^{III} in the presence of increasing concentrations of cationic and anionic surfactants separately as well as in their mixtures.

Ga^{III} under the chosen experimental conditions yields sharp maximum which occurs at -1.28 V (S.C.E.) and that it lies on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero whose potential is -0.47 V (S.C.E.) under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of Ga^{III} ($\approx -1.10 \text{ V}$) lies on the

negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the maximum of Ga^{III} is of negative polarity².

Effect of increasing concentrations of surfactants on the maximum: The effect of increasing concentrations of cationic and anionic surfactants, separately as well as in their mixtures, on E_{max} and i_{max} has been studied and the values are shown in Figs. 1a-c. It is seen that E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials as the concentration of the surfactants is increased, and i_{max} decreases, from $19.10 \mu\text{A}$ (in the absence of surfactants) to different values just before the suppression of the maximum.

Relative efficacies of surfactants in suppression of the maximum: The maximum suppression point³ (M.S.P.) is defined as the concentration of the surfactant precisely sufficient to eliminate the maximum under consideration. It is computed by plotting the value of i_{max}/i_d vs log of concentration of the surfactant and extrapolating to the concentration axis at which i_{max}/i_d is unity. The M.S.P. values for different surfactants separately and in their mixtures are listed in Table 1. A perusal of Table 1 reveals that M.S.P. values for cationic surfactants are much less than those for anionic ones. It follows that the amount of ionic surfactants required to suppress the maximum of similar sign is greater than that for those possessing dissimilar charges⁴. Antweiler⁵ has unambiguously proved that the polarographic maximum of the first kind is due to tangential streaming of the solution with respect to the drop. The success of a suppressor depends on its capability of curbing this streaming. Since the maximum in the present study lies on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the cationic surfactants will move right up to the mercury surface and the anionic ones are likely to move at a distance somewhere in the double layer. A cationic surfactant will prevent streaming more effectively as compared to an anionic one with identical hydrocarbon chain. This is supported

Fig 1. C-V curves of Ga^{III} in presence of increasing concentrations of (a) LPC: (1) 0.0, (2) 1.00×10^{-6} , (3) 2.00×10^{-6} , (4) 3.00×10^{-6} , (5) 4.00×10^{-6} , (6) $4.98 \times 10^{-6} M$, (b) SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) 3.00×10^{-4} , (3) 5.00×10^{-4} , (4) 1.00×10^{-3} , (5) 1.50×10^{-3} , (6) $2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, and (c) LPC+SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) $2.0 \times 10^{-7} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$, (3) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$, (4) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$, (5) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$, (6) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 2. Electrocapillary curves of Ga^{III} in presence of increasing concentrations of (a) LPC: (1) 0.0, (2) 1.00×10^{-6} , (3) 2.00×10^{-6} , (4) 3.00×10^{-6} , (5) 4.00×10^{-6} , (6) 4.98×10^{-6} M; (b) SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) 3.00×10^{-4} , (3) 5.00×10^{-4} , (4) 1.00×10^{-3} , (5) 1.50×10^{-3} , (6) 2.00×10^{-3} M, and (c) LPC+SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) $2.00 \times 10^{-7} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$, (3) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$, (4) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$, (5) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$, (6) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M.

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE VALUES OF M.S.P. FOR THE MAXIMUM OF Ga^{III} IN RESPECT OF CATIONIC AND ANIONIC SURFACTANTS SEPARATELY AND IN THEIR MIXTURES

Surfactant	M.S.P. M	Cationic + Anionic surfactants	M.S.P. M
Cationic			
LPC	4.98×10^{-6}	LPC+SLS	1.97×10^{-3}
OPC	8.96×10^{-6}	LPC+Manoxol-OT	4.97×10^{-4}
OPB	5.93×10^{-6}	LPC+Tergitol-7	2.93×10^{-3}
OTAB	4.94×10^{-6}	CPC+SLS	2.45×10^{-3}
CDBAC	4.96×10^{-6}	OPC+Manoxol-OT	3.59×10^{-4}
		CPC+Tergitol-7	1.95×10^{-3}
Anionic			
SLS	1.95×10^{-3}	CPB+SLS	1.96×10^{-3}
Manoxol-OT	5.12×10^{-4}	CPB+Manoxol-OT	3.57×10^{-4}
Tergitol 7	1.90×10^{-3}	OPB+Tergitol-7	2.97×10^{-3}
		OTAB+SLS	2.96×10^{-3}
		OTAB+Manoxol-OT	3.56×10^{-4}
		OTAB+Tergitol-7	1.93×10^{-3}
		CDBAC+SLS	2.45×10^{-3}
		CDBAC+Manoxol-OT	2.58×10^{-4}
		CDBAC+Tergitol-7	2.95×10^{-3}

by the fact that LPC is more effective than SLS, though both the surfactants have the same carbon chain length.

On the basis of M.S.P. values, the following order for the relative efficacies of cationic and anionic surfactants in suppressing the negative maximum of Ga^{III} has been established: cationic surfactants, LPC > CTAB > CDBAC > CPB > CPC; anionic surfactants, Manoxol-OT > Tergitol-7 > SLS.

Electrocapillary curves and adsorption characteristics of surfactants. The electrocapillary curves in the presence of different concentrations of cationic and anionic surfactants separately as well as in their mixtures, have been shown in typical Figs. 2a-c. In the absence of a surfactant, the

potential of the electrocapillary zero is -0.47 V (vs S.C.E.) under the chosen experimental conditions. In the presence of increasing concentrations of surfactants, however, a change in the shape of the electrocapillary curve occurs. The electrocapillary zero gets shifted to less negative potentials in the case of cationic surfactants and to more negative potentials in the case of anionic surfactants, but in the case of mixtures of the two, this shift occurs to more negative potentials.

The values of interfacial tension have been obtained from electrocapillary curves for the potential (-0.9 V), on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero. It is seen that interfacial tension (γ) decreases as the concentration of the surfactants increases. This implies positive adsorption as is shown by increasing positive values of ΓRT calculated by Gibb's adsorption equation⁶,

$$\Gamma = -\frac{C}{RT} \cdot \frac{d\gamma}{dC}$$

The value of $d\gamma/dC$ has been obtained from γ vs C plots. Thus, the addition of surfactants leads to their adsorption on the electrode surface and that they are carried away by the motion of the mercury and of the electrolyte to the place of greatest surface tension. They accumulate there and decrease the surface tension thereby creating a force against the streaming and ultimately bring about the suppression of the polarographic maximum.

Additive and antagonistic effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants: The additive and antagonistic effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants have been ascertained by determining their M.S.P. values separately and in their

mixtures. The M.S.P. values in respect of various surfactants, viz. LPC, CPC, CPB, CTAB and CDBAC (cationic); SLS, Manoxol-OT and Tergitol-7 (anionic); and the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7; CPC+SLS, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS, CDBAC+Manoxol-OT, and CDBAC+Tergitol-7, have been determined and listed in Table 1. A perusal of Table 1 shows that the M.S.P. values in respect of the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7, CPC+SLS, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS, CDBAC+Tergitol-7 are much larger than those for individual surfactants thereby indicating antagonistic effects of these mixtures in the suppression of the maximum of Ga^{III} . This is further supported by the fact that the values of I_{RT} , in each case, at the concentration of surfactant at which the maximum gets just suppressed are lower for these mixtures than those for individual surfactants.

It is interesting to note that M.S.P. value in respect of the mixture of CDBAC and Manoxol-OT is equal to half of the individual M.S.P. value, thereby indicating that this mixture shows neither additive nor antagonistic effect in suppressing the maximum of Ga^{III} . Further, it is also interesting to note that none of the probable mixtures of the two surfactants (*i.e.* cationic and anionic) shows the additive effect in the suppression of negative polarographic maximum of Ga^{III} .

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Viscosity of Electrolyte Solutions

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THE search for an equation of fluidity which would account for the variation of viscosity of electrolyte solutions with concentration over a wide range dates back to the early days of solution chemistry. But till now hardly any progress has been achieved in concentrated electrolyte solutions, particularly beyond 0.1 *M*. In this respect the model proposed by Goldsack and Franchetto¹ who based their derivation of the equation of fluidity on the absolute rate theory successfully explains the viscosity results of simple electrolyte in highly concentrated solutions, extending nearly to saturation. Another approach was made by Angell^{2,3} who adopted the equation of fluidity based on the free volume theory of liquids to fused salt mixtures and electrolyte solutions by proposing that the only parameter dependent on the electrolyte concentration is T_0 , the glass transition temperature. Assuming a linear dependence of T_0 on the electrolyte concentrations, N in equivalent per litre, Angell² put forward the following equation of fluidity of electrolyte solution,

$$1/\eta = Ae^{-k'/(N_0 - N)} \quad (1)$$

where, A and k' are two parameters supposed to be independent of composition and N_0 is the hypothetical concentration at which the glass transition would occur.

Roy Choudhury and Majumdar⁴ modified equation (1) by incorporating the condition that $\eta \rightarrow \eta_0$, the viscosity of the solvent as $N \rightarrow 0$, so that it becomes

$$\ln \eta_{rel} = \frac{k'N}{N_0(N_0 - N)} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) has been shown to be valid for the concentration dependence of the viscosity of quaternary ammonium halides⁴⁻⁶ in aqueous solutions for wide range of concentration for suitable values of N_0 . Moreover, this equation in the dilute solution range led to Jones-Dole equation without the Falkenhagen term and one could identify the k'/N_0^2 with the B coefficient of Jones-Dole equation.

In view of these results, it would be worthwhile to test the validity of equation (2) for an electrolyte in a non-aqueous solvent and at several temperatures. We have examined equation (2) with respect to temperature dependence of the viscosity of simple electrolytes, KCl and NaCl in aqueous solutions as well as the concentration dependence of viscosity at a fixed temperature of lithium chloride in *N,N*-dimethylformamide.